

The Death Row Truth

Capital punishment is against the better judgment of modern criminology, and, above all the highest expression of love in the nature of God. -Martin Luther King Jr.

According to The innocence project, Troy Davis was executed by the state of Georgia on Sept 21, 2011, on the doubtful accounts of murdering a police officer, something he established did not occur. His last words were pleading forgiveness for his executioners and strength for his family (Innocence Project). Davis is just one of the 529 Black men that have been executed since 1976 stated by The Death penalty information center (Executions Overview). The death penalty must be abolished.

Racial Bias

The National Registry of Exonerations states that innocent Black people are about seven times more likely to be convicted of murder than innocent white people. Therefore, using the death penalty as capital punishment is unrightful due to racial disparity occurring when someone is convicted which more likely will be a Black person than a white person (Race and Wrongful Convictions in The United States).

According to the NAACP, African Americans only make up 13% of the population in the USA yet make up 35% of the individuals executed within the last 40 years, this appalling disproportion between the population size of African Americans and those convicted of the death penalty shows that there are disparities in the criminal justice system (Criminal Justice Fact Sheet).

As reported by UW sociology professor Katherine Beckett, Black defendants in the State of Washington were four times more likely to receive the Death penalty than defendants of other races. This staggering study is what led the death penalty to be abolished in Washington state (Seattle Times).

As stated by the legal scholar Charles Ogletree, "the racially disproportionate application of the death penalty can be seen as being in historical continuity with the long and sordid history of lynching in this country." Racial Bias is deeply rooted in the legal system lynching being historically the source of the death penalty (Black Man's Burden: Race and the Death Penalty in America).

Cruel and Unusual Punishment

Recent autopsies published by NPR showed that "84% of lethal injections used in most death penalty executions lead to pulmonary edema according to the 200 autopsies that were reviewed."¹ The report explains that lungs enlarge twice the size of normal lungs and create the effect of organ failure, this method is cruel, inducing a perceptible painful death. (Investigations NPR).

According to The Constitution Center, the supreme court found the death penalty to be unconstitutional" The Court holds that the imposition and carrying out of the death penalty in these cases constitute cruel and unusual punishment in violation of the Eighth and Fourteenth Amendments." During the ruling of *Furman v. Georgia*, The Court temporarily found the death penalty to be cruel and unusual therefore unconstitutional (Constitution Center Blog).

¹ This detailed article has some breaking research on lethal injections, sections such as problem in every step explaining in detail how lethal injections often have faults due to pharmaceutical errors and IVs being placed by nonmedical personnel.

In a recent article of The American Bar Association, Justice Breyer argues that the penalty is unusual due to its decline in application "(effectively 86% of counties have no death penalty) Within the United States to abandon the use of the death penalty, and that this decline in the imposition and implementation of the death penalty has rendered it an unusual punishment. "Most counties in the USA do not have a death penalty and the lack of use shows that it is an unusual punishment (Death Penalty Representation Center).

The Amnesty International claims the death penalty breaches human rights, "Amnesty International holds that the death penalty breaches human rights, in particular the right to life and the right to live free from torture or cruel, inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment. Both rights are protected under the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, adopted by the UN in 1948." In accordance with the UN the death penalty violates human rights due to being barbaric (Death penalty).

Deterrence

According to an article published by Heritage, the death penalty deters crime in three diverse ways "that said, the death penalty serves three legitimate penological objectives: general deterrence, specific deterrence, and retribution.

The first, general deterrence, is the message that gets sent to people who are thinking about committing heinous crimes that they shouldn't do it or else they might end up being sentenced to death.

The second, specific deterrence, is specific to the defendant. It simply means that the person who is subjected to the death penalty won't be alive to kill other people.

The third penological goal, retribution, is an expression of society's right to make a moral judgment by imposing a punishment on a wrongdoer befitting the crime he has committed.

Twenty-nine states, and the people's representatives in Congress have spoken loudly; the death penalty should be available for the worst of the worst." This article argues that the death penalty deters crime by sending message to the public, by removing the killer from society, and lastly by imposing a societal moral right (Heritage Foundation)

The death penalty as a matter of fact does not deter crime, according to ACLU "No, there is no credible evidence that the death penalty deters crime more effectively than long terms of imprisonment. States that have death penalty laws do not have lower crime rates or murder rates than states without such laws. And states that have abolished capital punishment show no significant changes in either crime or murder rates. "In accordance with this article there is no evidence that the death penalty deters crime by message, specific deterrence or moral right since the states that do have the death penalty don't have lower crime rates (The Death penalty: Questions and Answers).

Call to action

The death penalty originates from a dreadful history and has claimed many lives such as Troy's Davis, but action can be taken, and differences have been made to further advance the justice system. The Death penalty Action organization is a source of action" Find our prisoner specific case work when especially striking cases of innocence, racism and injustice have associated actions you can take with our petitions for Rodney Reed (Texas), Anthony Apanovitch (Ohio), Richard Glossip (Oklahoma), James Dailey (Florida) and more." This source is able to help the public to sign petitions, participate in active legislation and more. Change is possible and believe it will be made.(Death Row Case Work).

Work Cited

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